

IDEA-FAST

Identifying Digital Endpoints to Assess FAtigue, Sleep and acTivities in daily living in Neurodegenerative disorders and Immune-mediated inflammatory diseases

Grant Agreement No. 853981

WP1 – Project Coordination & Oversight

D1.2: Risk assessment process and management procedure

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1 Abstract

This document details the procedure within IDEA-FAST by which the project risks are identified, categorised and monitored. The most important, critical risks are already described in Annex I of the Grant Agreement. Additional risks will be identified as part of the project review and planning process.

2 Introduction

The IDEA-FAST Risk Assessment Procedure is a controlling document that incorporates the goals, strategies and methods for performing risk management on the project. It describes all aspects of the risk identification, estimation, evaluation and control processes. The purpose of developing such a plan is to allow risk management on the project to be performed in an effective manner.

Every project has an overall goal, which is usually split into a number of well-specified sub-goals and associated deadlines by when the various goals should be reached. Every goal carries a risk that it will not be reached as specified and/or within the required deadline. This risk has to be managed so as to minimise the probability that the end goal of the project will not be reached. The Risk Assessment document formalises a procedure for the identification, assessment and mitigation of risk within the IDEA-FAST project.

Risks are assessed against likelihood of occurrence and the severity of any impact. These are then ranked into three classes (I, II or III, with III being the most critical), depending on whether the assessments are low, medium or high. A list of risks will be maintained by the Project Manager, as shown in Appendix A. Each risk will also have a log which details any mitigation actions and changes to the risk status, as shown in Appendix B.

The most important, critical risks are already described in Annex I of the grant agreement. Additional risks will be identified as part of the project planning steps, particularly during the development of the WP action plans at the start of each year.

3 Roles and Responsibilities

The IDEA-FAST Project Manager is responsible for the implementation of the Risk Assessments and for maintaining an audit log of the identified risks and associated actions. The WP leaders are responsible for identifying the risks associated with their WP, for assessing the likelihood and severity of the risks, for proposing mitigation actions where relevant, and for identifying the key partners to be involved. This can be done through reference to the project deliverables and milestones, together with their own knowledge of the project, or through a formal risk assessment workshop or brainstorming session. Individuals can also report any identified risks to the relevant WP leader. The WP leader should then report any identified risks and mitigation actions to the Project Manager.

The Project Manager is also responsible for highlighting the most important risks to the Project Coordination Team (PCT) and the Steering Committee to ensure that planned mitigation actions are discussed and approved.

4 Risk Management Steps

The following risk management steps will be carried out at the overall project level and at the WP level:

1. Define detailed goals
2. Identify risks that might endanger successful completion of the goals
3. Assess and rank the risks according to classes

4. Define risk mitigation measures, particularly for the highest class risks (category II/III)
5. Introduce mitigation measures in the project plan, implement and monitor them

4.1 Define detailed project goals

While Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement defines the overall objectives of the project, it does not cover in great detail the various goals and specifications required to be met along the way. To address this, a detailed set of critical timepoints and activities for all work packages have been identified, as well the elements needed to achieve these. Through an ongoing goal-oriented process of project planning and review, these are updated and the project risk profile adjusted.

4.2 Identify risks that might endanger successful completion of the project goals

An essential requirement for the risk management process is that each individual working on any of the work packages within the project should contribute to this step. All existing risks should be recorded, even if they seem unlikely to happen and even if a risk mitigation measure seems quite obvious or is already being implemented. The ownership of the risk (WP and partner) should also be identified.

4.3 Assess and rank the risks according to classes

The risks identified in the previous step should be ranked according to the likelihood and severity of the risk, as described below. The results of this task are recorded in a risk assessment table, provided in Appendix A. Risks should be numbered according to the WP they relate to, e.g. R2.1 for the first risk identified related to WP2.

4.3.1 Likelihood of Risk

The likelihood or probability that a potential risk will occur will be classified into one of three categories:

Low	Low probability
Medium	Medium probability
High	High probability

4.3.2 Impact of Risk

The estimated severity or level of impact of the risk, if it were to occur, will be classified into one of three categories:

Low	Less than 2 months expected delay on project planning; AND Less than 2 person-months expected additional effort required; AND Less than 20 k€ expected additional project cost.
Medium	More than 2 months but less than 6 months expected delay on project planning; OR More than 2 person-months but less than 6 person-months expected additional effort required; OR More than 20 k€ but less than 60 k€ expected additional project cost; AND Back-up solutions can readily be identified and can be made available.
High	More than 6 months expected delay on project planning; OR More than 6 person-months expected additional effort required; OR More than 60 k€ expected additional project cost; OR The concerned aspect of the project cannot be completed as planned.

4.3.3 Risk Categories

Based on the above rankings, risks will be classified into one of three risk classes as follows:

		PROBABILITY		
		Low	Medium	High
SEVERITY	Low	Class I	Class II	Class II
	Medium	Class II	Class II	Class III
	High	Class III	Class III	Class III

Project risk management at the overall project level and at the WP level will mainly focus on Risk Class II and III.

Note: this simplified risk assessment and management scheme is deemed to be appropriate for the IDEA-FAST project.

4.4 Define risk mitigation measures

Risk mitigation measures and back-up solutions will be defined for at least the higher class (Class II/III) risks.

4.5 Introduce mitigation measures in project plan and implement

Plans for dealing with identified risks including mitigation measures will be recorded and monitored through the Risk Management Audit Log, shown in Appendix B. Where relevant, these plans will also be incorporated into revised work plans.

4.6 Regularly review the risks and mitigation measures

Risks and mitigation actions will be regularly reviewed by the Project Manager and WP leaders (at least every 6 months for the overall risk log). However, the most critical risks will be discussed at least monthly, at the regular PCT teleconferences. This includes the escalation of more than one or two WP-level class II/III risks that in combination may give rise to a greater risk to the overall project delivery (so that individual risks are not reviewed in isolation).

5 Conclusions

The risk assessment process described above will be run at the WP level, coordinated by the WP leaders, and at the project level by the project management team.

A Risk Management Plan will be established for each WP and the overall project. This will be reviewed and approved by the Project Manager and Project Coordination Team (PCT).

WP leaders will be requested to review the risk assessments and the Risk Management Audit Log in their quarterly reports and update as appropriate.

Appendix A – Risk Assessment Table

No.	WP	Risk	Probability			Impact	Severity			Risk Class*
			L	M	H		L	M	H	
R1.1										
R1.2										
R2.1										

* – Risk class as defined in section 4.3.3, or state “N/A” if a risk is no longer applicable (and provide details in Risk Management Audit Log).

Appendix B – Risk Management Audit Log

No.	Risk*	Ownership	Potential Risk Mitigation	History / Actions
R1.1				1.
R1.2				1.
R2.1				1.